

Supplementary Figure 1

A

B

C

D

E

F

Supplementary Figure 2

A

B

- Categories**
- Pathway
 - Module
 - Enzyme
 - Reaction
 - Compound

- Diagnose**
- ▭ Con
 - ▭ SCH
 - ▭ CH

Supplementary Figure 3

A

B

Supplementary Figure 4

Supplementary Figure 5

Feature ID :FT1242
 Exp Precursor m/z :367.157565930618
 Exp rt :27.0910000002
 Score: 0.999993153782523
 Compound: Dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate
 Adduct: [M-H]
 Ref Precursor m/z: 367.157919696
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: CZWCKYRVOZZJNM-USOAJAOKSA-N
 KEGG ID: C04555
 Reference Source: HMDB

Feature ID :FT4125
 Exp Precursor m/z :894.617534354759
 Exp rt :148.92199999998
 Score: 0.581823904076767
 Compound: PC 40:5
 Adduct: [M+CH3COOH-H]
 Ref Precursor m/z: 894.6211
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: MAAMGQXOTCBPFS-CYDMDVBXSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: MassBank

Feature ID :FT2227
 Exp Precursor m/z :540.328466411571
 Exp rt :205.704
 Score: 0.504639074915504
 Compound: 1-Palmitoylphosphatidylcholine
 Adduct: M+HCOO
 Ref Precursor m/z: 540.331
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: ASWBKHCZGQVJ-VUHFFFAOYSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT0245
 Exp Precursor m/z :144.079370046866
 Exp rt :257.63899999998
 Score: 0.578299591556027
 Compound: Tryptophol
 Adduct: [M-H2O+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 144.08
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: MBBOMCVGYCRMEA-UHFFFAOYSA-N
 KEGG ID: C00955
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT2559
 Exp Precursor m/z :482.321267378197
 Exp rt :209.532
 Score: 0.667833879657436
 Compound: LysoPC(15:0/0:0)
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 482.324
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: RJZVWDTYEWCUAR-JOCHJYFZSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT3375
 Exp Precursor m/z :764.522057390621
 Exp rt :37.50499999998
 Score: 0.543386102066635
 Compound: PE 38:5
 Adduct: [M-H]
 Ref Precursor m/z: 764.5266
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: ZYMZKMPPJPQHY-HAGCXRLMSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: MassBank

Feature ID :FT1698
 Exp Precursor m/z :452.276136334077
 Exp rt :203.02399999998
 Score: 0.955814158684626
 Compound: LysoPE(16:0/0:0)
 Adduct: [M-H]
 Ref Precursor m/z: 452.278
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: YVYMBNSKXOXSKW-HXUWFJFHS-A
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Supplementary Figure 6

Feature ID :FT1242
 Exp Precursor m/z :367.157565930618
 Exp rt :.27.09100000002
 Score: 0.999993153782523
 Compound: Dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate
 Adduct: [M-H]
 Ref Precursor m/z: 367.157919696
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: CZWCKYRVOZZJNM-USOAJAOKSA-N
 KEGG ID: C04555
 Reference Source: HMDB

Feature ID :FT2227
 Exp Precursor m/z :540.328466411571
 Exp rt :.205.704
 Score: 0.504639074915504
 Compound: 1-Palmitoylphosphatidylcholine
 Adduct: M+HCOO
 Ref Precursor m/z: 540.331
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: ASWBKHCZGQVJV-UHFFFAOYSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT2559
 Exp Precursor m/z :482.321267378197
 Exp rt :.209.532
 Score: 0.667833879657436
 Compound: LysoPC(15:0/0:0)
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 482.324
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: RJZVWDYEWCUAR-JOCHJYFZSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT2986
 Exp Precursor m/z :524.371133869361
 Exp rt :.205.02199999998
 Score: 0.883236460330108
 Compound: LysoPC(18:0/0:0)
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 524.37
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: IHNKQIMGVNPMT-CRUZDIDTESA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT2808
 Exp Precursor m/z :508.373122614267
 Exp rt :.199.203
 Score: 0.626636721355765
 Compound: LysoPC(P-18:0/0:0)
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 508.375
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: WBOMIOWRFPZMC-AYICAFKVSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT3225
 Exp Precursor m/z :552.399207113849
 Exp rt :.202.503
 Score: 0.906233857272661
 Compound: LysoPC(20:0/0:0)
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 552.401
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: UJATOAILWGVYRQS-HHHXNRCSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT0201
 Exp Precursor m/z :132.101646761972
 Exp rt :.257.589
 Score: 0.887483652731619
 Compound: (±)-erythro-Isoleucine
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 132.102453665
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: AGPKZVBTJJNPAG-UHFFFAOYSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: HMDB

Supplementary Figure 7

Feature ID :FT0201
 Exp Precursor m/z :132.101646761972
 Exp rt :.257.589
 Score: 0.887483652731619
 Compound: (±)-erythro-Isoleucine
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 132.102453665
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: AGPKZVBTJNPAG-UHFFFAOYSA-N
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: HMDB

Feature ID :FT0410
 Exp Precursor m/z :184.093609711541
 Exp rt :.320.655
 Score: 0.987282625355371
 Compound: L-Carnitine
 Adduct: M-H+Na
 Ref Precursor m/z: 184.094
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: PHIQXFUZVPYII-ZCFIWBFS-A-O
 KEGG ID: NA
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT0255
 Exp Precursor m/z :147.042834908578
 Exp rt :.303.40099999998
 Score: 0.672006504072013
 Compound: 4-Hydroxycinnamic acid
 Adduct: [M-H2O+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 147.044
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: NGSWKAQJWJESNS-ZZXKWWIFSA-N
 KEGG ID: C00811
 Reference Source: GNPS

Feature ID :FT0269
 Exp Precursor m/z :150.057079542358
 Exp rt :.281.73700000002
 Score: 0.962443314023904
 Compound: Racemethionine
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 150.058
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: FFEARJCKVFRZRR-UHFFFAOYSA-N
 KEGG ID: C01733
 Reference Source: MoNA

Feature ID :FT0286
 Exp Precursor m/z :156.075899076752
 Exp rt :.392.91
 Score: 0.981368954936881
 Compound: L-Histidine
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 156.077301547
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: HNDVDQJGIGZPNO-YFKPBYRVSA-N
 KEGG ID: C00135
 Reference Source: HMDB

Feature ID :FT0258
 Exp Precursor m/z :147.111382690542
 Exp rt :.391.64500000002
 Score: 0.957436305188103
 Compound: L-Lysine
 Adduct: [M+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 147.113352702
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: KDXKERNBIXSRK-YFKPBYRVSA-N
 KEGG ID: C00047
 Reference Source: HMDB

Feature ID :FT0218
 Exp Precursor m/z :136.073620654127
 Exp rt :.302.286
 Score: 0.544007416854604
 Compound: p-Octopamine
 Adduct: [M-H2O+H]⁺
 Ref Precursor m/z: 136.076
 Ref rt: NA
 INCHIKEY: QHGUCRYDKWKLGM-QMMMGPBSA-N
 KEGG ID: C04227
 Reference Source: GNPS

Supplementary Figure 8

(a)

(b)

C

